

**MODERN EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES AND PEDAGOGICAL
INNOVATIONS AS A TOOL FOR EDUCATION QUALITY
MANAGEMENT**

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Abstract. The basis of educational quality management is the transition from teaching methods to the introduction of educational technologies into the educational process. The article discusses several definitions of educational technology.

Keywords: quality of education, management, teaching methods, criterion, student, teacher.

Improving the quality of education is one of the main tasks of modernization of education in Uzbekistan. In modern pedagogy, the most important criterion of pedagogical skill is the effectiveness of the teacher's work, which is reflected in the learning ability of schoolchildren and interest in science. That is, a teacher should be a skilled pedagogue who knows how to teach all children without exception. A teacher's professionalism is most evident in the good results of students who are usually considered unwilling, unable to learn, or incompetent.

The basis of educational quality management is the transition from teaching methods to the introduction of educational technologies into the educational process.

How to distinguish the concepts of "methodology" and "educational technology"?

Methodology is a pedagogic science that studies the laws of teaching a specific subject. Teaching methods are methods of work of the teacher and students, with the help of which the acquisition of knowledge, skills and qualifications is achieved, the outlook of students is formed, and abilities are developed. The concept of "methodology" represents the mechanism of applying a set of methods, methods, tools and conditions of teaching and training.

If the methods determine the activity of the teacher in the lesson (what to present and in what order, what tools to use, what problems to solve, how to organize the synthesis of material, etc.), then in educational technologies, as a rule, students' own activity is described.

If the methods have a soft, prescriptive nature (the teacher has the right to more or less follow the recommendations of the teaching manuals for teachers), then the technologies are specific actions for the students and the teacher. determines the sequence. control actions that violate the integrity of the educational process, which can prevent the achievement of the planned result.

There are many definitions of educational technology, in which GK Selevko emphasizes the following criteria for production at one level or another. Such criteria include conceptuality, consistency, controllability, efficiency, and reproducibility.

Criterion of conceptuality - each of the technologies is based on one or more theories (philosophical, pedagogical or psychological). For example, programmed learning is based on behaviorist theory; developmental education - integrated technology on the theories of educational activity and meaningful generalization - based on the idea of expanding didactic units, etc.

Durability is characterized by the logic of construction, the interdependence of elements, the completeness and structure of materials and activities.

Management ability - the ability to effectively manage the educational and cognitive activities of students by setting diagnostic goals; designing the learning process; "Built-in" management that allows you to adjust the process of choosing results and teaching tools and methods.

Effectiveness includes achieving the planned result with the optimal use of funds and time for training.

Reproducibility refers to the ability of technology to be replicated, transferred, and borrowed by other teachers.

The practical implementation of the methodology is the teacher's lesson plan, which shows, in particular, a certain sequence of steps, the actions of the teacher and sometimes students.

Technology includes:

- diagnostic goal setting: planning of educational results through the actions of students mastered in a certain segment of the educational process. These actions are written with verbs: learn, identify, name, give examples, compare, apply, etc.; goals can also be determined using a multi-level task system;

- the existence of a certain technological chain of pedagogical and educational actions leading to the planned result;

- the existence of one or more pedagogical or psychological theories based on each technology;

- the ability to reproduce the technology by any teacher, because the technology is built on objective scientific foundations that do not depend on the personality of the teacher;

- availability of diagnostic procedures, including indicators and tools for measuring results; These procedures represent the input, current, final control necessary to correct the knowledge, skills and the learning process itself.

References

1. I. Lerner. Yes. Didakticheskie osnovy metodov obucheniya / I. Yes. Lerner. Moscow: Pedagogy, 1981. 186 p.
2. N. A. Kulemin. Kvalimetrichesky monitoring upravleniya kachestvom obrazovaniya: concept, technology, model: monograph / N. A. Kulemin. Izhevsk: Alfabeta, 2000. 187 p.
3. R. Akhliddinov Management of education in Uzbekistan: problems, research, solutions / R. Akhliddinov, D. Aldroyt, A. Khodjaev, F. Nasyrova, M. Kamilova. - Tashkent: ES - JASIS, 1999.
4. S.Z. Gulyamitdinov, L.V. Peregudov. Nauchno-metodicheskie osnovy obespecheniya kachestv i konkurentosposobnosti kadrov // Educational problems. - 1998. - No. 3.
5. Sh. Kurbanov, E. Seytkhalilov. Upravlenie kachestvom obrazovaniya: monogr. - Tashkent: Shark, 2004.
6. V. Kvasha. Pedagogicheskie innovatsii kak obekt upravlencheskoy deyatel'nosti // Diagnostika v pedagogicheskom tvorchestve: sb. Nauch. tr. - M., 1996. - C. 37-42.
7. V. V. Levshina Formirovanie sistemy menedzhmenta kachestva vuza: monograph / V. V. Levshina, E. S. Buka. Krasnoyarsk: Izdvo Sib. Mr. tech. unta, 2004. 324 p.